

Paper 25

CREDIT RISK MANAGEMENT WITH FOCUS ON THE COOPERATIVE BANKING SECTOR

Arati.N.Rawal

Research scholar, Department of commerce, Rani Chennamma University, Belgavi,
Mail.Id: aru265@gmail.com

Abstract

Credit risk is one of the most common risk in the cooperative banking sector. It is the hidden feature, if not timely controlled, will negative impact on banking business. The credit risk management is need for an hour therefore, it is very necessary to implementing the credit risk management processes in the banking transactions. It helps the banks in identifying, measuring, monitor and control the credit risk.

The purpose of the present study is to focus on the state of credit risk management process in cooperative banks in Dharwad district. Further, the paper makes an assessment of the extent to which cooperative banks were following the standard practices and identify the focus area of improvement in near future.

Keyword: credit risk management process,

Introduction

Credit risk is always associated with banking business, and taking risk is the important part of any banking operation to earn the profit and growth. By being exposed to the risk banks have faced lot of problems, the banks have realized that credit risk is important and the bank need to identify, measure, monitor and control the risk very significant. Due to this the effective management of credit risk has become the critical component of approaching risk management.

The credit risk management is defined as the borrower will fail to pay principle amount with interest in accordance with agreed terms. The main objective of credit risk management is to minimize the risk and maximize the profit.

The purpose of the present study is to focus on the state of credit risk management process in cooperative banks in Dharwad district. Further, the paper makes an assessment of the extent to which cooperative banks were following the standard practices and identify the focus area of improvement in near future.

Need for the study

The credit risk management provides a framework for understand the nature of credit risk presented in the banking organization. While credit risk management helps the bank in maximizing the profitability and more precisely to help the credit officers to improve in

future. Therefore, a need was felt by the researcher to understand the of credit risk management processes helps the banks in identify, measure, monitor and control the risk of cooperative banking sector. Hence the study entitled “Credit risk management with focus on cooperative banking sector in Dharwad district.

Literature review

Anupam Mitra (2012): The study attempt to identify the credit risk emerged as biggest risk for cooperative banks, which evidence arises due to rising of non-performing assets of banks and also have inference of politicians in the organizations. The study concluded that to control and reduce the non-performing assets, bank should adopt the strategies of pre sanction in depth and post sanction supervision follow up.

Bodla and Richa verma (2009): The authors examine the credit risk management in commercial banking sector. The study observed that risk rating is most important instrument, and proper credit administration, prudential limits, risk pricing help the bank in mange the credit risk effectively.

Research objective and methodology

The main objective of the study is access the risk profile of cooperative banks; to examine the credit risk management processes of managing key risk areas.

The data relating to the research includes both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected through the questionnaire and secondary data has been collected through the Reserve Bank of India guidelines, journals, books.

Analysis of the study

The analysis of the study based on all ten cooperative banks which are situated in Dharwad district. There are total eight cooperative banks which are operating in urban area and two cooperative banks are operated in rural area. All the banks are following the Reserve Banks of India guidelines to manage credit risk. The information is collected from the credit officers at head office level. The credit risk management helps the banks in long term success of banking business.

Credit risk management processes

The credit risk management process contains the four elements to successfully manage the risk, such are identifying, measuring, monitoring and controlling the risk within a time. The banks have to identify with pre-sanctioning process by implementing the KYC norms and collecting the proper documentation. Measure the risk by pricing the credit and by assess the credit scoring of the borrowers. The risk monitored at organizational level by constituting the committees and by fixing the credit exposure limits. The credit risk controlled by the bank, with periodically loan review mechanism and by collecting collateral security from borrowers.

A. Identify the credit risk

Credit risk is identification various risk associated with the banking organisation. Generally credit risk is identified most important for the banking business. While, identify the risk within the time helps the banks in decision making process. The bank have identify the credit risk by KYC norms.

KYC norms (Know Your Customer)

The KYC norm is required for the banks to verify the borrowers address through documents listed in the circular. It has been noticed by the RBI that a large number of persons, especially. Those belonging to low income group, both in urban and rural area are not able to produce such documents to satisfy the bank about their identity and address. This leads to their inability to access the banking services and result in their financial exclusion. It involves the true identification of credit beneficiaries, source of funds, nature of customers business etc. The KYC norms helps the banks understand their customers and their financial dealings better and help them manage their risk prudentially.

The study found that all the Urban and Rural area sample banks have following the RBI guidelines by implementing the KYC norms (RBI/2015-16/42).

Table 1
KYC norms

KYC norms	Urban area banks	Rural area banks	Total
Yes	8 (80)	2 (20)	10 (100)
	(100)	(100)	(100)
No	0 (00)	0 (00)	0 (00)
	(00)	(00)	(00)
Total	8 (80)	2 (20)	10 (100)

Source: Field survey

Note: Figures in brackets opposite to the figures in the cells represent the percentage of the respective cell figures to the respective row total.

: Figures in brackets below the figures in different cells represent the percentage of the respective figures to the total of the respective columns.

Table 1 reveals that out of 8 urban area banks all the sample banks have following the practice of KYC norms and out of 02 rural area banks all the sample banks have following the practices of KYC norms.

B. Measure the credit risk

The credit risk is measurement should be comprehensive enough to cover all the significant sources of risk exposures. The measurement process should be based on the accuracy of information available. The credit risk measured by the bank can be collected through CIBIL to identify the credit history of the borrowers. Further, bank have pricing the credit depending on the risk factor.

Credit Information Bureau (CIBIL)

The RBI has made compulsory to all the cooperative banks to register the credit information bureau to identify the credit history of borrowers. It provide the information regarding credit history of borrowers. There are three credit information bureau are registered by the cooperative banks are Equifax, Experian and Highmark. They are Equifax credit Information Services Pvt. Ltd. High Mark Credit Information Services Pvt. Ltd.; Experian Credit Information Company of India Pvt. Ltd (RBI/2009-10/84).

Table 2
Members of Credit Information Bureau

Credit Information Bureau	Urban area banks	ural area banks	Total
Experian	1 (100)	0 (00)	(100)

	(13)	(00)	
High mark	3 (60) (38)	2 (40) (100)	(100)
High mark and Equifax	1 (100) (13)	0 (00) (00)	(100)
Highmark and Experian	1 (100) (13)	0 (00) (00)	((100) (10)
High Mark, Experian and Equifax	1 (100) (13)	0 (00) (00)	(100)
Not registered	1 (100) (13)	0 (00) (00)	(100)
Total	8 (80)	2 (20)	(100)

Source: Field survey

Note: Figures in brackets opposite to the figures in the cells represent the percentage of the respective cell figures to the respective row total.

: Figures in brackets below the figures in different cells represent the percentage of the respective figures to the total of the respective columns.

Table 2 observed that 01 urban area sample banks have registered all the three CIB are Equifax, Experian and Highmark and 01 sample banks have registered Highmark and Equifax.

Further, 01 sample bank have registered Highmark and Experian and 03 sample banks are registered only High mark. However, 01 urban area sample bank have registered Experian only and 01 urban area sample bank have not registered Credit Information Bureau. Whereas 02 rural area sample banks have registered Highmark only.

Credit pricing

Risk-based pricing, in its simplest terms, is the alignment of loan pricing with the expected loan risk. Typically, a borrower's credit risk is used to determine whether a loan application will be accepted or declined. That same risk may also be used to drive the loan price. This means charging a higher interest rate for a higher-risk transaction and a lower rate for a lower-risk transaction. Additionally, risk-based pricing builds on the net interest margin calculations by adding to the cost of funds.

The study observed that out of 8 sample banks, 04 urban area sample banks have credit pricing on basis of cost of funds, 03 urban area sample banks have pricing the credit on the basis of price quoted by cost of funds, competitors and market conditions. Further, 01 urban area sample banks have credit pricing on the basis of future business potential.

However, 01 rural area sample banks have pricing the credit on the basis of cost of funds and 01 rural area of sample banks have pricing the credit on the basis of price quoted by cost of funds, competitors and market conditions.

C. Credit risk monitoring

Credit risk monitoring is most necessary for the banking business because risk profile changing over a period, it is necessary monitor risk profile on an ongoing basis. Risk

monitoring is process maintained by the organisational structure and by fixing the credit exposure limits.

The organisational structure has monitoring the credit by constituted the committees such as credit policy committees, credit data management cell, credit audit committees.

Table 3
Credit risk monitoring committees

Committees	Urban area banks		Total	Rural area banks		Total
	Yes	No		Yes	No	
Credit policy committees	06	02	08	01	01	02
Credit audit committees	05	03	08	02	00	02
Credit counselling cell	03	05	08	00	02	02
Credit data management cell	06	02	08	02	00	02

Source: Field survey

Note: figures in the table represents number of committees.

Table 3 represents that out of 8 urban area banks, 06 sample banks have framing the credit policy committees and 05 sample banks have framing the credit audit committees. Further 03 sample banks have framing the credit counselling cell and 06 sample banks have framing the credit data management cell.

It was observed that out of 02 rural area banks, 01 sample bank have framing the credit policy committee and all the sample banks have framing the credit audit committee and credit data management cell. However, none of the sample bank have framing the credit counselling cell.

Credit exposure limits

The banks have diversify the credit by fixing the credit exposure limits to concentrate the credit to different sectors to monitoring the risk, such as single borrowers exposure limits, group of borrowers exposure limits, priority sector and weaker sector limits and industrial sector limits.

The Reserve Bank of India has set the limits to single borrower's limits 15% of cost of funds and 40% for group of borrowers and for 40% for priority sector lending and 10% for weaker sector.

- The study observed that the both urban and rural area sample banks have following RBI guidelines to single borrower's exposure limits that is 15% of capital funds.
- The group of credit exposure limits of both urban and rural area banks have low concentration on group of credit exposure limits that is below the 40% of capital funds. It indicates that the sample banks have low concentration or avoid the risk.
- The credit exposer limits to priority and weaker sector lending, the urban and rural area banks have high concentrate on the priority and weaker sector lending. It is high risk for bank.

D. Control the credit risk

Credit risk control means taken the action to reduce the risk or control the bad debt in the banks.

Usually banks have control the credit risk by periodic monitoring the accounts, loan review mechanism conducted by credit officers and chartered accountants.

Loan review mechanism or credit audit

The bank have control the credit risk by periodically audited the bank branches. The both urban and rural area banks have periodically audited the bank branches. There is three types of credit audit has been conducted by cooperative banks; internal audit, external audit and credit risk inspection.

- **Internal audit:** The internal audit is conducted by credit officers on quarterly and monthly bank branches depending on the banking business. Both the urban and rural area banks have internal audited the bank branches on quarterly and monthly basis.
- **External audit:** The urban and rural area sample banks have external audited the banks on yearly basis appointed by external auditors.
- **Credit risk Inspection:** The CRI is an auditor's simultaneous internal check of the transactions and recorded documents of the banks. It is mandated by the RBI in association with the Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI), to select from the list chartered accountants for the banks inspection. They are close monitoring of loans and advances and check the records. If the chartered accountant rectify the any irregularities bring to the notice of the board.

The Chartered accountants are inspect the banks and reporting the compliances, it grade the banks on their audit reports. Such as A, B, C and D grades are given to the banks. The grade A and B banks have a with good audit reporting and C and D grade sample banks have poor performance or considered as poor audit report banks.

The summarized findings are:

- The study found that all the urban and rural area sample banks have following the practices KYC norms, while sanctioning credit.
- The urban and rural are banks have registered the Credit Information Bureau and one of the urban area bank have not registered the credit information bureau.
- The urban and rural area sample bank have pricing the credit on the basis of cost of funds.
- The 75% of urban area sample banks have constituted the credit policy committee and credit audit committee, 35% of urban area sample banks have framing the credit counselling cell.
- The 50 % of rural area banks have constituted the credit policy committees and credit audit committees and credit data management cell and none of the bank have framing the credit counselling cell.
- The credit exposure limits: The single borrower's exposure limits the urban and rural area banks have following the RBI guidelines while single borrower's exposure limits.
- The group of exposure limit, urban and rural area banks have low concentrated on group of group of borrowers, it indicates the risk avoid by the bank.
- Credit exposure to priority and weaker sector lending, the urban area banks and rural area banks have high concentration on priority sector lending and wreaker sector lending, it indicates high risk for the banks.
- The urban and rural area banks have periodically audited the bank branches and external audit is conducted by chartered accountants, further, credit risk inspection is conducted by the cooperative groups.

Conclusion of the study

The credit risk management process provide the principle guidelines to the banks, to identify, measure, monitor and control the risk within a time. It helps the banks in reduce the risk in the banking business. However, the cooperative bank in Dharwad district must be improved regard credit risk management. Further, it must have concentrate on framing the committees, concentrate on credit exposure limits towards the group of borrowers and bank must have periodically review the credit risk management policy for updating and strengthen the banking business.

References:

1. Anupam Mitra (2012), "Evaluation of credit risk management in urban cooperative banks-A study in Hoghly district", the management account, March 2012, Pp. 328-348.
2. S. Bodla and RichaVerma (2009), "Credit risk management framework at banks in India", the ICFAI journal of bank management, vol. VIII, No.1, Pp. 47-72.
3. Hennie van Greuning Sonja BrajovicBratanovic (2010), "Managing Banking risk", A JAICO book Mumbai.
4. S.N.Bidani, P.K. Mitra, Pramod kumar; "credit risk management" Taxman's allied service private limited.
5. Programme on risk management for state and central cooperative banks, BIRD, Mangalore, 2015.
6. www. RBI guidelines.